

Dioxygen Complexes of the Heavier 4d and 5d Transition Metal Ions*

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Dioxygen complexes of the heavier transition metal ions of the 4d and 5d series are in general more stable than those of the 3d series and many of the complexes can be isolated and studied. In most of these complexes dioxygen is coordinated in an edge-on "dihapto" fashion. Vaska's complex $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{O}_2)$ has been the most well studied complex in this series and was the first to be isolated.

New end-on complexes of Ru(III) with triphenylarsine and water soluble complexes with EDTA and HEDTA have been prepared and characterized. Besides the Co(II)-dioxygen carrier which are quite well known, the ruthenium(III)-dioxygen complexes are the only examples of reversible coordination of dioxygen aqueous solution.

DIOXYGEN complexes of transition metal ions have gained much importance in recent years because of their oxygen transport and their participation in oxidation reactions¹. Dioxygen complexes are defined as those complexes in which two oxygen atoms are bonded together and are also coordinated to one or two metal ions. These complexes are formed either by the direct coordination of dioxygen to a metal ion in a low oxidation state followed by charge transfer to and from dioxygen to the metal ion or by the direct interaction of H_2O_2 or superoxide ion with a metal ion in a higher oxidation state. The two routes, however, give rise to the same type of complexes² and in many cases their formation involves a reversible coordination of dioxygen to the metal ion from which either dioxygen or H_2O_2 can be generated under suitable conditions and electron shift reactions. The charge transfer from the metal ion to the dioxygen moiety may vary from a small extent as in oxyhaemoglobin³ to the formation of a formal superoxide, O_2^- , or peroxide, O_2^{2-} , anions by the transfer of one or two electrons to O_2 , respectively. The extent of charge transfer to dioxygen in a given complex is computed mainly on the basis of the O^{17} hyperfine splitting of the epr signal in dioxygen complexes.

The existence of dioxygen complexes in biological systems was first recognized when oxyhaemoglobin, the carrier of O_2 in vertebrates blood was characterized³ as a 1:1 Fe(II)-dioxygen complex. The bent end-on coordination of dioxygen to the Fe(II) ion in oxyhaemoglobin was postulated by Pauling³ in 1936 and confirmed by the X-ray structure of the complex by Phillips⁴ in 1978. Decammine- μ -peroxodichromium(III) ion, $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CrO}_2\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{4+}$ was the first synthetic dioxygen complex which was thoroughly characterized by Werner⁵ in 1898. In subsequent years, Werner and his group⁶ isolated several μ -peroxo and double bridged μ -peroxo- μ -hydroxo or imido double bridged complexes of Co(III). The practical applications of synthetic oxygen carriers started around 1940 when Calvin and his coworkers⁷ demonstrated the oxygen absorption and desorption properties of the Co(II) Schiff's base complex, bis-salicylaldehydeethylenediiminecobalt(II), 'Salcomine'. In subsequent years work on Co(II)-dioxygen carriers in solution was done by a group of investigators^{8,9} notably by Martell and coworkers^{10,11}. In the last decade notable contribution to metal-dioxygen che-

mistry was made by Basolo and coworkers¹² who worked on manganese-porphyrinatodioxygen complexes and Collman and his group¹³ who synthesized sterically protected Fe(II) porphyrin complex that acts as haemoglobin model¹⁴.

Work on the dioxygen complexes of heavier transition elements of the 4d and 5d series made its beginning after the discovery of chlorocarbonylbis(biphenylphosphine)iridium(II)dioxygen complex, $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{O}_2)$ by Vaska¹⁵ in 1965. Since the discovery of Vaska's complex, about hundred dioxygen complex of 4d and 5d transition elements were prepared and the structure of about forty of these complexes is now known¹. The present article will be confined to these complexes. Excellent reviews^{11,12} deal with the dioxygen complexes of the 3d transition metal ions. The classification of the complexes discussed is based on the type of coordinated dioxygen to metal ion.

I. 1:1 η^2 -Peroxo complexes :

The term dihapto η^2 -peroxo is used in this article for edge-on coordinated complexes of dioxygen where both the ends of oxygen are considered to be coordinated to a single metal ion.

In the 4d and 5d series of transition elements such complexes are formed by two routes: a direct interaction of metal ions in $\text{M}^{+1}(\text{d}^9)$ or $\text{M}^0(\text{d}^{10})$ configuration with dioxygen and the subsequent formation of $\text{M}^{+2}(\text{d}^8)(\text{O}_2^{2-})$ or $\text{M}^{+2}(\text{d}^8)(\text{O}_2^-)$ complexes, respectively. Such reactions may be broadly considered to be oxidative addition reactions of dioxygen with the metal ion. Reaction of $\text{M}^{+2}(\text{d}^7)$ metal ions with H_2O_2 in the presence of suitable ligands also give rise to the η^2 -peroxo complexes. Most of the peroxo complexes of group V and group VI transition metal ions like Nb(V), Ta(V), Mo(VI) and W(VI) were obtained by this route¹⁶.

a) Dioxygen complexes of nd^8 elements, Rh(I), Ir(I) :

Extensive work on Vaska's complex has been done in regard to its structure¹⁷ which shows a dihapto coordination of dioxygen to the metal ion.

* Dedicated to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra ; teacher, friend, philosopher and scientist, on the occasion of his sixtieth birthday.

The ir spectra of this complex and other η^2 -peroxo complexes give peaks around $840\text{--}870\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of a coordinated peroxo group in the complex. Dioxygen is reversibly coordinated in the complex $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$. The oxygen absorption and desorption studies have indicated that the coordinates of dioxygen to the metal ion is accompanied by a favourable enthalpy (12 to 13 e. u.) and large negative entropy (-22 to -24 e. u. change which is characteristic of an oxidative addition reaction involving a polar transition state. Various analogues of Vaska's complex were prepared¹ by the variation of the anionic group from Cl^- to F^- , Br^- , I^- , CN^- , NO_3^- , $\text{RC}=\text{C}^-$, C_6H_5^- , XC_6H_4^- and the π -acidic triphenylphosphine ligand to various arylalkyl phosphines and arsines. Neutral iridium(I) dioxygen complexes in the absence of CO are relatively unstable. Thus, the complex $\text{IrCl}(\text{O})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ is very poorly characterized¹⁸.

The rhodium(I) analogue of Vaska's complex $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})\text{Cl}(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ does not react¹⁹ with O_2 , indicating that the presence of highly π -acidic ligands like CO is not essential for the dioxygen complex formation in the 4d series. Mild π -acidic ligands like isonitriles can stabilize²⁰ the rhodium(I) dioxygen complexes of the type $\text{RhCl}(\text{O}_2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{RNC})$ ($\text{R} = t\text{-Bu}$, C_6H_{11} , $p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$). Unlike Ir(I), rhodium(I) gives very stable²¹ dioxygen complexes of the type $\text{RhCl}(\text{O}_2)(\text{L})_3$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$, AsPh_3).

Stable cationic dioxygen complexes of Rh(I) and Ir(I) of the composition $\text{ML}_4(\text{O}_2)\text{A}$, [$\text{M} = \text{Rh}(\text{I})$, $\text{Ir}(\text{I})$, $\text{L} = \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}$, AsMe_2Ph , $\text{A} = \text{BPh}_4^-$, BF_6^-] were isolated and characterized^{21,22}. Polydentate phosphines also yield stable dioxygen complexes with Rh(I) and Ir(I). The Rh(I) dioxygen complexes of polydentate phosphines are more stable than the monodentate phosphines.

Bis-1,2-diphenylphosphinoethane (diphos) gives stable^{23,24} complexes of the type $\text{M}(\text{diphos})_2(\text{O}_2)\text{A}$ with Rh(I) and Ir(I). Taqui Khan and Martell²⁵ reported the cationic dioxygen complexes of Rh(I) and Ir(I) of the composition $\text{RhL}(\text{O}_2)\text{Cl}$ with tetradentate phosphines, tetraphos-1 ($\phi_2\text{PCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{P}\phi_2$) and tetraphos-2, - $\text{P}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{P}\phi_2)_3$. The yellow orange dioxygen complexes are very stable in solution and in the solid state. Novel *bis*-dioxygen complexes of the hexaligand bimetallic ligands, TDDX and TDADX of the composition $\text{M}_2(\text{TDDX})\text{Cl}_2(\text{O}_2)_2$ [$\text{M} = \text{Ir}(\text{I})$, $\text{Rh}(\text{I})$] and $\text{Rh}_2(\text{TDADX})\text{Cl}_2(\text{O}_2)_2$ were reported

by Taqui Khan *et al*^{26,27}. These novel complexes have dioxygen coordinated to each metal centre in the binuclear complex (Fig. 1). These binuclear complexes are models for surface activation of molecular oxygen where more than one metal centre is involved in complexation with the diatomic molecule.

b) Dioxygen complexes of nd^8 elements Ru^0 and Os^0 :

$4d^8$ complexes of Ru^0 formally stabilized by NO or CO groups react with dioxygen to form well characterized dioxygen complexes. Brown diamagnetic dioxygen complexes of the composition $\text{RuX}(\text{NO})(\text{O}_2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- , OH^- , NCS^- , NCO^- , CN^- , N_3^- , NO_3^-) were isolated²⁸ by the oxygenation of the complexes, $\text{RuX}(\text{NO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ in the solid state and in solution. Examples of Rh^0 and Os^0 dioxygen complexes stabilized²⁹ by CO are $\text{M}(\text{CO})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{O}_2)$. Dioxygen reacts with the four coordinate nd^8 complexes $\text{M}(\text{CO})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ to form the six coordinate formal $\text{Ru}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Os}(\text{II})$ complexes of the composition $\text{M}(\text{CO})_2(\text{O}_2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2$. The $\text{Os}(\text{II})$ complex, $\text{Os}(\text{CO})_2(\text{O}_2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ is the only example of an osmium-dioxygen complex reported so far.

c) Dioxygen complex of the nd^{10} elements Pd^0 and Pt^0 :

Wilke *et al*³⁰ reported dioxygen complexes of $\text{Pd}(\text{O})$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{O})$ of the composition $\text{M}(\text{PPh}_3)_3(\text{O}_2)$ [$\text{M} = \text{Pd}(\text{II})$, $\text{Pt}(\text{II})$] by the oxygenation of $\text{M}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ in dry benzene. The platinum(II) complex is more stable than the $\text{Pd}(\text{II})$ complex which is the order of stability expected for the complexes of transition metals $5d > 4d > 3d$. Hydride³¹ elimination from $\text{PtH}_2(\text{PR}_3)_2$ ($\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}$, $i\text{pr}$) by CO in the presence of air resulted in the formation of the dioxygen complexes $\text{Pt}(\text{O}_2)(\text{PR}_3)_2$ admixed with $\text{Pt}(\text{CO}_2)(\text{PR}_3)_2$. The latter complex is formed by the oxidation of CO to CO_2 within the coordination sphere of the metal ion in the complex $\text{Pt}(\text{O}_2)(\text{PR}_3)_2$. The $\text{Pd}(\text{O})$ complex $\text{Pd}(t\text{-BuNC})_4$ reacts³² with O_2 in benzene to form the dioxygen complex $\text{Pd}(\text{O}_2)(t\text{-BuNC})_2$. The dioxygen complexes of $\text{Pd}(\text{O})$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{O})$ are very reactive and take part in oxygen atom transfer reactions.

II. 2 : 1 Dihapto- μ -peroxo complexes :

Suzuki *et al*^{33,34} isolated dihapto- μ -peroxo complexes of Rh(I) of the composition $\text{Rh}_2(\text{dien})_2(\text{O}_2)$ ($\text{dien} = \text{cycloocta-1,5 diene}$), by the reaction of the

Fig. 1. $\text{L} = \text{P}$, (TDDX), $\text{L} = \text{As}$ (TDADX)

Reaction 1

bridged complex $M_2(\text{dien})_2\text{Cl}_2$ with KO_2 in CH_2Cl_2 (Reaction 1).

The reaction may be visualized as the replacement of the chloro bridged anions by the peroxy group obtained by the autooxidation of two molecules of KO_2 .

In the case of Pd(II) the reaction³⁴ of the chloro bridged organometallic Pd(II) complex^{3a} with KO_2 in CH_2Cl_2 gives the dihapto- μ -peroxy complex of Pd(II)^{2b} (Reaction 2).

The dihapto- μ -peroxy Pd(II) complex 2b reacts with CH_3CN to give the μ -peroxy Pd(II) complex 2c. Reaction 2 is an interesting case of the conversion of a dihapto- μ -peroxy complex to a bent-end-on- μ -peroxy species.

III. 2 : 1 Bis-dihapto-peroxy complex :

A novel binuclear bis-dihapto complex of Rh(I) of the composition $[\text{RhCl}(\text{O}_2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2]_2$ was obtained by Bennett and Donaldson³⁵ by the oxygenation of $\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ in benzene solution. The structure of the dimeric complex can be represented in terms of a trigonal bipyramidal coordination of two

Fig. 2

rhodium atoms. The complex may best be described as a bis-dihapto- μ -peroxy complex where one of the peroxy oxygens binds two formal rhodium(III) ions through two ion pairs while the other oxygen atom is coordinated in a monohapto manner to only one Rh(III) ion (Fig. 2).

IV. 1 : 1 Superoxo and 1:2- μ -superoxo complexes of Rh(III) :

The 1 : 1- μ -peroxy complexes of 4d and 5d transition elements are rather less known and have started to be recognized recently. These complexes are formed by metal ions in a comparatively higher oxidation state. Cillard *et al*³⁴ have reported a 1:1 superoxo complex of Rh(III) of the composition $[\text{Rh}(\text{en})_2(\text{NO}_2)(\text{O}_2^-)]^+$ by exposing a solution of $[\text{Rh}(\text{en})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]^+$ to sunlight in the presence of O_2 . The complex exhibits a strong Raman band at 1052 cm^{-1} characteristic of a superoxo group.

In the presence of aquorhodium(III), the red monomeric superoxo complex is converted to the blue or purple dimeric species, $[\text{X}(\text{en})_2\text{RhO}_2\text{Rh}(\text{en})_2\text{X}]^{m+}$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$ or H_2O). The complexes are paramagnetic and are the counterparts of the 3d⁶ superoxo complexes of Co(III) which are very well known.

V. 1 : 1- μ -Peroxo complexes of Ru(IV) :

The binuclear peroxo complexes of the (4d⁶) Ru(IV) ion have been recently reported by Taqui Khan and Veera Reddy³⁶ and Taqui Khan and Ramchandiraiah³⁷. A solution of $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot (\text{AsPh}_3)_3$ reacts with O_2 in benzene solution to form the μ -peroxy complex, $[(\text{AsPh}_3)_3\text{Cl}_2\text{RuO}_2\text{RuCl}_2(\text{AsPh}_3)_3]\text{Cl}_2$. The complex is paramagnetic with the μ_{eff} value corresponding to two unpaired electrons per ruthenium ion, supporting a spin paired Ru(IV) configuration for the metal ion. The ν_{O_2} frequency in the complex is observed at 845 cm^{-1} corresponding to a coordinated peroxo species. The presence of a peroxo group in the complex is also supported by the photoelectron spectrum of the dioxygen complex which shows a peak at 532 eV corresponding to a peroxide group. The $4d_{5/2}$ photoelectron peak indicates that arsenic is in a trivalent state thus ruling out the 845 cm^{-1} stretch as due to $\nu_{\text{As}=\text{O}}$. The electronic spectrum of the complex exhibits spin allowed bands at 520 nm ($E=1696$) and 410 nm ($E=4162$) which may be assigned to $3T_1 \rightarrow 3T_2$ and $3T_1 \rightarrow 3E$ transitions respectively in a distorted octahedron. There is

Fig. 3

also an intense band observed at 380 nm involving the L→M charge transfer for the peroxy group. The complex has been assigned the structure as shown in Fig. 3.

Taqui Khan and Ramchandraiah have recently reported²⁷ the dioxygen complexes of Ru(II) in aqueous solution with EDTA and HEDTA. A 1:1 solution of RuCl₂-EDTA and HEDTA, when titrated with a base in the presence of dioxygen indicate the formation of -μ-peroxy-μ-hydroxo complexes. The log K $\frac{ML_2H_2O_2}{(ML)_2(O_2)(OH)}$ values for L=EDTA and HEDTA complexes are 29.8±0.2 and 22.1±0.2 respectively. By the gas absorption measurements the number of oxygen molecules bound to the metal chelate were found to be one mole per two moles of the metal complex. Conductivity data on the aqueous solution of the complexes indicate that they are 3:1 electrolytes. The O₂ of the coordinated peroxy group in the complexes are at 897 cm⁻¹. The coordinated peroxy group can be displaced from the complexes by the addition of a strong acid. The iodometric estimation gives the evidence of one mole of peroxide to be bound per mole of the -μ-peroxy complex. The LMCT bands of the peroxy group²⁵ are observed at 331 and 345 nm. The dioxygen complexes are reversible with respect to oxygen uptake. The structure of the complexes is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4

The Ru(III) EDTA or HEDTA-dioxygen complexes are the first examples of the -μ-peroxy complexes of a 4d transition element in aqueous solution and in the solid state. The Co(III)-μ-peroxy complexes as mentioned in the beginning of this article are known from the time of Werner.

The dioxygen complexes of heavier transition metal ions hold lot of promise in future as catalysts in various oxidation and atom transfer reactions of molecular oxygen¹. One of their possible applications is in the design of fuel cells where oxygen can be reduced to water at a potential of 1.23 volts.

References

1. "Homogeneous Catalysis by Metal Complexes", M. M. TAQUI KHAN and A. E. MARTELL, Academic Press, N. Y., 1974, Vol. 1.
2. L. VASKA, *Accs. Chem. Research*, 1976, 1, 175.
3. L. PAULING and C. CORYELL, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, (U. S. A.), 1936, 22, 210.
4. S. E. V. PHILLIPS, *Nature*, 1978, 273, 247.
5. A. WERNER and A. MYLIUS, *Ann.*, 1898, 16, 246.
6. A. WERNER, *Ann.*, 1910, 1, 375.
7. "Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds", A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, Prentice Hall, N. Y., 1950.
8. S. FALLAH, *Chimia.*, 1967, 21, 538 ; 1969, 23, 177.
9. F. MILLER and R. G. WILKINS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 92, 2687 ; K. WATERS and R. G. WILKINS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 752.
10. G. MCLENCLON and A. E. MARTELL, *Coord. Chem. Reviews*, 1976, 19, 1.
11. W. R. HARRIS, J. H. TIMMONS and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1979, 8, 251 ; J. H. TIMMONS, A. CLEARFIELD, A. E. MARTELL and R. H. NISWANDER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, 18, 1042 ; 1979, 18, 2977 ; S. R. PICKENS and A. E. MARTELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 15.
12. F. BASOLO, B. H. HOFFMAN and J. A. IBERS, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1975, 8, 384 ; R. D. JONES, D. A. SUMMERVILLE and F. BASOLO, *Chem. Revs.*, 1979, 79, 139.
13. J. P. COLLMAN, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1977, 10, 245.
14. J. P. COLLMAN, in "Metal ion Activation of Dioxygen", (Ed.) T. G. SPIRO, Plenum, N. Y., 1980.
15. L. VASKA, *Science*, 1963, 104, 809.
16. C. W. BALKE and E. F. SMITH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 1637 ; H. MIMOUN, I. SEREE, DE. ROCH and L. SAGIS, *Bull. Soc. Chem. Fr.*, 1969, 1481.
17. M. S. WEININGER, I. F. TAYLOR, JR. and E. L. AMMERA, *Chem. Commun.* 1971, 1172.
18. H. VAN GAAL, H. G. A. M. CUPHERS and VANDER ENT, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 1694.
19. L. VASKA and J. PEONE, JR., *Kemistilehti*, 1971, B44, 317.
20. A. NAKAMURA, Y. TATSUNO and S. OTSUKO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 2058.
21. M. J. BENNETT and P. B. DONALDSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 16, 1582.
22. J. T. MAGUE and G. WELKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 1736.
23. L. M. HAINES, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 1685.
24. J. A. MCGINNETY, N. C. PAYNE and J. A. IBERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 630.
25. M. M. TAQUI KHAN and A. E. MARTELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 2964.
26. M. M. TAQUI KHAN and A. E. MARTELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 14, 674.
27. M. M. TAQUI KHAN, RAFEEQ MOHIUDDIN, MEHREEN AHMED and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1980.
28. K. R. LAING and W. R. ROPER, *Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 1556 ; 1970, 1272.
29. B. E. CAVIT, K. R. GRUNDY and W. R. ROPER, *Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 60.
30. G. WILKE, H. SCHOTT and P. HEIMBACH, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1967, 6, 92.
31. H. C. CLARIS, A. B. GOEL and C. S. WONG, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1979, 34, 159.
32. S. OTSUKA, A. NAKAMURA and Y. TATSUNO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 81, 6994.
33. F. SAKURAI, H. SUZUKI, Y. MOROOKA and T. IKAWA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 102, 7863.
34. H. SUZUKI, K. MIZUTANI, Y. MOROOKA and T. IKAWA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 748.
35. R. D. GILLARD, J. D. PEDROSA, DE. JESUS and L. R. H. TIPPING, *Chem. Commun.*, 1977, 58.
36. M. M. TAQUI KHAN and K. K. VEERA REDDY, *J. Coord. Chem.* (In press).
37. M. M. TAQUI KHAN and RAMCHANDRAIAH, *Inorg. Chem.* (In press).